

Inclusion Management and Organisational Effectiveness in Selected FMCG Companies in Lagos State, Nigeria

Olumuyiwa Oluseun Adeoye (PhD) and Ebenezer Adebisi Alo (PhD)

Department of Business Administration, Adeleke University, Nigeria

muyiwa.adeoye@adelekeuniversity.edu.ng

ebenezer.alo@adelekeuniversity.edu.ng

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7890818

Abstract

Inclusion remains an important concept in the management of any organisation. The continuing growth of organisational performance is supported by research from many different fields, particularly inclusive management. As the workplace distinctiveness gets higher, unexpected difficulties, discrimination and workplace issues for members of marginalised groups are all on the rise. The study examined the connection between organisational success and inclusion implementation in selected FMCG companies in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study used a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 8,039 employees of FMCG companies in Lagos State, Nigeria, out of which 381 employees were sampled. A regression model was employed to analyse the hypotheses formulated for the study. Findings revealed that a change in management accessibility by a unit induce an increase in productivity by 1.152 which was significant at $p < 0.05$ and a unit change in performance teams showed an increase in competitiveness by 1.010 which was statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ level of significance. The study concluded that a substantial correlation exist between managerial accessibility and organisational productivity with performance teams and organisational competitiveness at work. This study therefore recommended that FMCG companies should take every precaution to prevent unfairness and high levels of inequality which demoralises and inhibits employees' effective performance

Keywords: Inclusion, Inclusion management, Organisational effectiveness, Productivity, Performance teams

Introduction

Certainly, the importance of management inclusion for existing and anticipated organisations is evident given the numerous complaints of employee annoyance caused by what they consider to be inequality, prejudice, and a lack of inclusiveness at work. An unpleasant and ubiquitous problem in the workplace is inequity. It is vitally important to Nigeria's organisational management in the long term. One aspect of inclusion is leveraging distinctiveness for the good of the organisation (Randel et al., 2018). The elements that make up the concept of inclusion are understanding, openness, consideration, and empathy. Inclusion is defined by equitable participatory opportunities. Considerations must be shown to every individual's special skills, expertise, and viewpoints. Building a growing organisation is another aspect of inclusion (Brown, 2019). Cultivating a workplace that welcomes people with varied identities, traits, and ways of thinking is a key component of inclusion inside organisations. Individuals must be appreciated, acknowledged, and engaged in order to create a workplace of inclusion (Nilsson & Nilsson, 2021). An atmosphere that is inclusive maximises the uniqueness of every worker (Chen et al., 2023). Inclusion refers to organisational procedures that guarantee that workers and teams from all ethnicities are embraced, accepted, and considered equitable on a traditional and economic level. Inclusion is a sense of belonging for everybody within an organisation that is built on respect and value (Hasan, 2022).

Admitting that being motivated from the bottom up, organisational inclusion is steered from the top down (Gbadegesin et al., 2022). Due to allegations of low productivity from some identified groups, bosses at organisations are constantly under pressure to halt the integration of organisational diversity. The weight is increasing at an uncontrollable rate. Organisations have reduced the steps they take to uphold their organisations' policy initiatives toward employee inclusivity as a result of the issue of subpar performance by some workers. Members of such targeted subgroups are becoming more disillusioned with their achievements (Mulugeta, 2022). If organisations want inclusion to succeed, individuals must cultivate a sense of commitment and involvement. People must perceive their value and involvement (Amah & Oyetunde, 2020). Shift in intentions and emphases may have an impact on organisational inclusion. Organisations that are inclusive must

keep pushing for improvements (Thompson et al., 2022). Inclusion is the driving force fuelling development (Kretschmer, 2022).

Fazzi (2023) described inclusion management as "patterns of managers' activities that stimulate the participation of employees, specialists in jointly addressing problems or concerns of interest." The term "Inclusive Management" will be used to describe workforce individuality and distinctiveness throughout this article. This viewpoint therefore aligns with Bell's (2021) expansive notion of inclusiveness, which states that individuals from all ethnicities and inclinations may be genuinely make major contributions to larger group efforts when they are involved in inclusion organisations, according to research. However, researchers and professionals have increasingly turned to recognition (workers perceiving that they are valued members of a work group or organisation as an outcome of treatment that satisfies needs for sense of community and uniqueness) as a pathway to achieving managerial efficiency in order to achieve more comprehensive involvement of diverse individuals in the workplace and to give all organisational members the opportunity to reach their full potential (Clement & Eketu, 2019). However, while it is obvious that inclusion in work groups can be beneficial, these experiences largely depend on efficient administration. It is noteworthy to mention that while researchers had also drawn attention to management issues raised by workplace uniqueness, there remain very few investigations and concepts. The researchers focused on management techniques that can tackle these concerns by encouraging employee perceptions of inclusion in work organisations. Managers that mostly encourage workforce inclusiveness connect with employees in approaches that go above and beyond preventing prejudice and discriminatory practices, particularly pledging to create value by maintaining a multicultural workplace (Okolie et al., 2020). Effective, cautious, and strategic use of all organisational resources is a key indicator of an organisation's ability to accomplish its specified goals (productivity, return on value, employee satisfaction, customer satisfaction).

The connection between activity outcomes and inputs is what is known as organisational effectiveness. According to Shehu and Clarke (2020), effectiveness is the ability to successfully produce or achieve a goal using the least amount of input possible. The ability of an organisation to produce a desired outcome or result is evidenced by its effectiveness. It is in the light of the forgoing that the current study was designed to examine the effect of inclusion management on organisational effectiveness among selected FMCG companies in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Literature review

The concept of inclusion management

The distinctive viewpoint of inclusive management focuses on how individuals from various backgrounds perceive and experience inclusion. "The extent to which employees feel that they are a part of major organisational activities, such as access to information and resources, involvement in work groups, and ability to influence decision-making," described by, Obiekwe et al. (2019), is referred to as inclusion. Inclusion, according to Mbah and Maduafor, (2022), is the extent to which individuals feel that their organisations take steps to include all employees in the vision and management of the company yet considering each employee's special abilities. Falola et al. (2020) claim that when individuals experience a sense of ownership and when inclusive activities, such as asking for and rewarding efforts from all employees, are really a constant component of the workplace, inclusion actually occurs. According to past studies, businesses can use a variety of strategies to promote an inclusive workplace. Employees may have the opportunity to participate in organisational outcome and operational procedures through initiatives and trainings that, for example, encourage job involvement and information sharing. All employees will be motivated to participate in training and performance initiatives since it promotes creativity and business success. Organisations must take action to promote equality and tolerance for individual differences in order to cultivate an inclusive culture (Ugoani, 2013).

Accessibility: Management of accessibility begins at the top. Leaders within the organisation must commit to the common value of inclusion in order for an accessibility management programme to be successful. The management must promote a workplace culture that values employees (high-medium-low level) as valuable contributors to the organisations community and clientele. If you don't know where you are, where you've been, or how to get there, you won't be able to predict where you're going. Understanding where your procedural and technical limitations are necessary for accessibility management. Then, it is necessary for management to create a dynamic working strategy to remove obstacles and enhance access for employees with a variety of disabilities, including mobility (Ahmed, 2017).

Programme Teams: Similarly, according to Nwabueze and Anike, (2016), "the team" refers to a group of individuals having complementing and acceptable academic, creative, or specialised talents. The team is in charge of carrying out the activities outlined in the programme or project plan, under the guidance of the programme manager or project manager. In order to increase work effectiveness, the process of building a project team enables teammates relationships to be improved both internally and externally, their competencies and talents to be developed, and the culture of the team as a whole to get optimised (Ogwueleka, 2015). A team needs its members to share the same vision and be driven to realize that vision in order to be genuinely effective. They must be dedicated to each other's participation in the project and have shared quantifiable goals.

Organisational effectiveness

Organisational effectiveness is a challenging and contentious concept. However, they differ on what effectiveness implies and how it is evaluated. Experts agree that it requires careful focus to goals, team cohesion, and linkages with the external environment (Super, 2020). However, the environment in where we live is ruled by effectiveness. Staff, supervisors, divisions, and businesses are continually expected to be effective, in order to put it simply, to produce outcomes. Early management theorists believed that success in managing organisations could best be predicted by individual's overall effectiveness. Effectiveness, according to Swanson et al. (1999), is related to achieving the cooperative aim, which is social and non-personal in nature. Wu et al. (2023), maintains that organisations cannot survive without effectiveness and that this effectiveness can be easily assessed. As Adamopoulos in his own sayings, "This society of ours can harmonise its two needs only through executive effectiveness: the needs of organisation to obtain from the individual the contribution it needs and the needs of the individual to have organization function as his tool for attaining his aims" (Adamopoulos, 2022). Taufique (2022) had previously proposed that individuals' actions in organisations should be intentional and integrated. "In light of the cacophony of viewpoints on organisational effectiveness, the seemingly simple but truly nuanced query is: in whom and what do we believe? This article's goal is to look at a few perspectives on organisational effectiveness, identify where they divide and agree, and offer some real-world solutions to the predicament that complexity has forced management, academics and professionals into.

Productivity: Despite the ambiguity surrounding the topic, this research has discovered a number of distinguishing traits that characterise the concept of productivity. Productivity is typically understood in industrial engineering to be the relationship between output (i.e., produced goods) and input (i.e., resources consumed) in the manufacturing transformation process as opined by Enrique et al. (2022). However, on the one hand, the utilisation and accessibility of resources is intimately related to productivity. This basically means that if a company's resources are misused or are insufficient, productivity will suffer. However, according to Nwankwere et al. (2017), value creation and productivity are closely related. High productivity is therefore attained when processes and resources used in industrial transformation add value to the final goods. In addition, things change for factors unrelated to productivity, such as inflation and other external circumstances that might have little to do with the effective use of resources. Nweke and Umanah (2022) argue that productivity, rather than profitability, is a better indicator of manufacturing excellence over the long term because profits are affected by a variety of factors from a short-term viewpoint.

Competitiveness: Businesses, now, must deal with customers' demands that are complicated, rapid environmental change, globalisation, and growing competition. This propensity for perpetual change, competition, and open markets increases the strain of competition on all businesses within the industry, promoting ideas like innovation, adaptability, and distinction from rivals (Akinyemi, 2022). Competitiveness has been researched at various levels, including the national, regional, industry, and corporate levels, by academics and practitioners. "The execution of a strategy not currently being employed by other enterprises that promotes the reduction of costs, the exploitation of market possibilities, and/or the neutralising of competitive risks" is how Harry et al. (2021), defined competitive advantage. At this level, competition takes into account a variety of variables that have an impact on the outcomes, including profitability, cost cutting, and product differentiation (Wu et al., 2022), among others.

The Theory of Generative Interactions

The Theory of Generative Interactions (GI) was propounded by George Herbert in 1934. The theory emphasised that across diversification, it builds on constructs and actual data from numerous academic disciplines such as sociology, social psychology, organisation studies and communications. According to the theory, overcoming numerous different exclusivist complexities (such as ego, speaking skills, stigmatising, and victimising) via adaptive cognitive handling and learning skills, as well as engaging in positive relationships, are essential for inclusion. This inclusion is then established and maintained by contextually relevant sets of management culture. Regarding a crucial, shared organisational goal, regularly integrating individuals over long periods of time, allowing different groups to have equal standing and insider status in contributing to success, and fostering participatory interconnectedness, interactional comfort, and personality are all conditions provided by organisational practices. The theory is appropriate to the present study since it compels individuals to re-examine assumptions they have about workplace culture and highlight significant questions about how companies work.

Empirical review

Younas et al. (2022) remarks that although relational leadership has hardly been studied in this context, research in the past has shown the critical role that leadership plays in encouraging workers to speak up. As a conclusion, the investigation looked at the relationship between leadership practice and inclusion management, a kind of leadership that values employee voice both personally and implicitly with workplace engagement. Employing information acquired from 252 employees and their respective supervisors working in transportation firms across the United Kingdom, this research demonstrates a favourable correlation between inclusion management and voice behaviour. The results validate the moderating impact of cognitive self-empowerment in the relationship between inclusion shared leadership and voice behaviour. In order to validate the findings and explore consequences, they employed causal attribution theory.

According to Kuknor and Bhattacharya (2022), their article seeks to examine the connections of organisational inclusion (OI) and inclusive leadership (IL) in literature as well as the roles that IL and OI play in the growth of human resources. Journals that have undergone external evaluation were used for the methodical literature review. A collection of 68 publications that focused on the connection between inclusion management and organisational inclusion were extensively examined for participation in the review. The study provides insights concerning how IL differentiates from other management philosophies and the behaviours of managers who embrace it. The article also provides a theoretical framework to show how IL and OI are related to one another. The study increased knowledge among academia and practitioners regarding the fallacy that only employees with disabilities are impacted by inclusion. The document assisted the interested parties in developing HRD practices. The article surveyed a topic that has received less attention and is one of the limited reviewed articles to look at the interactions involving IL and OI and how it affects HRD activities in an organisational setting.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey research design. This approach was appropriate for this study since it gave a thorough explanation of the relationship and impact of the variables under investigation. Three FMCG companies that have a valuation of not less than N400 billion were selected for the study out of the twenty (25) existing FMCG companies in Lagos State. The population of the study consisted of 8,039 employees of the three selected FMCG companies in Lagos State, Nigeria. A sample size of 381 employees was selected from the population through the application of Taro Yamane (1967) formula. A well-structured questionnaire was designed to capture the responses of the respondents. Three hundred and eighty-one (381) copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents from the three selected FMCG companies using convenience sampling techniques; out of which 325 copies representing 85.4% were returned and analysed using simple regression analysis technique.

The Taro Yamane formula is as applied below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where;

n = sample size

N = Total Population

e = Error term = 5%

Therefore;

$$n = \frac{8039}{1 + 8039(0.05)^2} = 381$$

Table 1: Analysis of the study population and sample size

S/N.	Name of selected companies in Lagos State	Market Capitalisation	Number of Employees	Sample Size
1	Bua Foods Plc.	N1.17tr	2500	104
2	Nestle Nigeria Plc.	N872bn	2201	158
3	Nigerian Brew Plc.	N421bn	3338	381
	Total		8,039	

Source: Researchers field survey (2022)

Results and discussion

A total of three hundred and eighty-one (381) copies of the questionnaire were administered on the employees of the three selected FMCG companies in Lagos State, Nigeria, out of which 325 copies representing 85.4% copies were returned and analysed.

Table 2: Cronbach’s alpha result

Variables	Cronbach’s Alpha Result
Management Accessibility	.986
Performance Teams	.821
Productivity	.994
Competitiveness	.993

Source: Researchers’ computation (2023)

For the study, Cronbach’s alpha coefficient was calculated to determine the reliability of the instrument. For Cronbach’s alpha coefficient, if the result shown is >0.75, the instrument is highly reliable, when it is between 0.5 - 0.74, the instrument is moderately reliable and when it is <0.5, it means that the instrument is less reliable. In a nutshell, the more the result shown tends to 1, the more the reliability of the instrument.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Management Accessibility	325	8.00	30.00	21.2462	7.16781
Performance Teams	325	9.00	86.00	21.6092	7.65244
Productivity	325	5.00	30.00	20.1446	8.31112
Competitiveness	325	5.00	30.00	19.5754	8.52581

Source: Researchers' computation (2023)

Test of hypotheses

Ho₁: Management accessibility has no significant influence on organisational productivity in selected FMCG companies in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Model summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.994 ^a	.988	.988	.91928	.988	26160.287	1	323	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), management accessibility

Source: Researchers' computation (2023)

The result of the regression model as contained in Table 4. The regression analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between dependent variable (management accessibility) against the independent variable (productivity). The Adjusted R Square which was .988, implies that 98.8% of the variations in productivity were caused by the variations in management accessibility as shown in the Table 4.

Table 5: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22107.246	1	22107.246	26160.287	.000 ^b
	Residual	272.957	323	.845		
	Total	22380.203	324			

a. Dependent Variable: productivity

b. Predictors: (Constant), management accessibility

Source: Researchers' computation (2023)

Table 5 shows that F-test was 26160.287, which was significant at 5%. This means that the model was well specified.

Table 6: Correlation coefficient for the relationship between management accessibility and organisational productivity

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	-4.340	.160		-27.168	.000
	Management accessibility	1.152	.007	.994	161.741	.000

a. Dependent Variable: productivity

Source: Researchers' computation (2023)

Table 6 shows the relationship between management accessibility and organisational productivity. It can be observed from the Table that taking all factors into consideration, all other factors held constant, productivity changed by -4.340. It was also found that with all other variables held at zero, a unit change in management accessibility led to an increase in productivity by 1.152

which was statistically significant at five per cent ($p - \text{value} = 0.000$). Based on the findings the null hypotheses was rejected which implies that management accessibility has a statistical significant influence on organisational productivity in the selected FMCG companies in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Table 7: Result of the correlation analysis

		Productivity	Management accessibility
Pearson Correlation	Productivity	1.000	.994
	Management accessibility	.994	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Productivity	.	.000
	Management accessibility	.000	.
N	Productivity	325	325
	Management accessibility	325	325

Source: Researchers' computation (2023)

The result of Table 4.7 revealed that there was a positive correlation between management accessibility and productivity with the value of .994 and the correlation relationship was highly significant given the Sig. value of .000. This positive correlation implied that an increase in improvement of management accessibility resulted in a corresponding increase in productivity.

H₀₂: Performance teams have no significant impact on organisational competitiveness in selected companies in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Table 8: Model summary

Model					Change Statistics				
	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.906 ^a	.821	.821	3.60978	.821	1484.407	1	323	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), performance teams

Source: Researchers' computation (2023)

Table 9: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	19342.554	1	19342.554	1484.407	.000 ^b
	Residual	4208.849	323	13.030		
	Total	23551.403	324			

a. Dependent Variable: competitiveness

b. Predictors: (Constant), performance teams

Source: Researchers' computation (2023)

The result of the regression analysis in Table 8 revealed that the Adjusted R Square is .821 which implies that 82.1% of the variations in competitiveness were caused by the variations in performance teams. This was further illustrated in the ANOVA Table 9. The result of the ANOVA shows that F-test was 1484.407 which were significant at 5%. This means that the model was well specified.

Table 4.10 shows that taking all factors into consideration, all other factors held constant, competitiveness change by -2.243. The findings presented also showed that with all other variables held at zero, a unit change in performance teams would lead to an increase in competitiveness by 1.010 which was statistically significant at 5 per cent going by the p value .000. Based on the result, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 10: Correlation coefficients to establish the relationship between performance teams and organisational competitiveness

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	-2.243	.601		-3.734	.000
	Performance teams	1.010	.026	.906	38.528	.000

a. Dependent Variable: competitiveness

Source: Researchers' computation (2023)

Table 10 presents the result of the correlation coefficient to determine the relationship between performance teams and organisational competitiveness. Taking all factors into consideration and all other factors held constant, competitiveness changed by -2.243 resulting in a unit change in performance teams. This led to an increase in competitiveness by 1.010 which was statistically significant at 5% (p-value = .000). Based on the result, the null hypothesis was rejected. It can therefore be concluded that there was a positive correlation between performance teams and competitiveness with the value of .906.

Table 11: Correlation result

		Competitiveness	Performance teams
Pearson Correlation	Competitiveness	1.000	.906
	Performance teams	.906	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Competitiveness	.	.000
	Performance teams	.000	.
N	Competitiveness	325	325
	Performance teams	325	325

Source: Researchers' computation (2023)

Discussion of findings

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was determined for the study to assess the instrument's reliability, and the findings indicated that the instrument is very reliable (>0.75). The first hypothesis adjusted R square, which was .988, suggested that changes in management accessibility were to account for 98.8% of fluctuations in productivity. The results demonstrated the link between organisational productivity and management accessibility. The researchers found that an increase in managerial accessibility of one unit resulted in a productivity boost of 1.152, which was statistically significant at 5% (p-value = 0.000). The finding in this investigation also conforms to the outcomes in the study of Harry et al., (2021) that reported positive results which indicated managerial accessibility has a significant impact on organisational productivity in the chosen FMCG companies in Lagos State, Nigeria, with the null hypothesis being rejected. The increase in management accessibility was inferred to raise production by this favourable link, according to the correlation. The second hypothesis showed an Adjusted R Square of .821, indicating that 82.1% of the differences in competitiveness were brought on by the differences in team performance. The ANOVA table, which implies that the F-test was 1484.407 being significant at 5%, provided additional evidence for this. It followed that the model was adequately specified. The results also demonstrated that, while all other parameters remained constant, a unit change in performance teams resulted in an upswing in competitiveness of 1.010, which, according to the p-value .000, was statistically significant at 5%. The conclusion rejects the null hypothesis. The finding is also in line with a similar positive result in the investigation considered by Nwankwere et al. (2017), which is evident that competitiveness and performance teams have a strong correlation with a rating of .906, in the selected FMCG companies in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Conclusion and recommendation

The goal of the study was to determine the connection between organisational effectiveness and the application of management inclusiveness. For the sake of succinctness, it should be noted that the results of this study demonstrated a favourable association between managerial inclusiveness and organisational effectiveness. The outcomes of the statistical tests demonstrated that there is a substantial correlation between managerial accessibility and organisational productivity; performance teams, and organisational competitiveness at work. More specifically, inclusion management of accessibility and performance teams created a room for innovation, appreciation and creativity related to Javed et al. (2021). These afford the organisations a competitive edge in varying marketplaces. In order to improve workplace productivity and enhance the company's competitive edge, managing inclusion in the workplace is an essential component of employee retention and attraction. Employee's engagement, which implies employee participation of change by actually implementing it, is fuelled by staff members who give response to concerns, assist one another, and are glad to work for the company. The study therefore, recommended that FMCG companies should take every precaution to prevent unfairness and high levels of inequality which demoralises and inhibits employees' effective performance. The workplace environment is regarded as pleasant or conducive since harassing, unfair employment discrimination, and bullying are not present, similar to the positive finding of the study by Kuknor and Bhattacharya (2022). Without a doubt, the adoption of workplace inclusion will be successful if, among other things, the workplace shows amicable connections between employees.

Limitations of the study and future research

In Lagos State, Nigeria, just three chosen Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) companies were included in the investigation which forms the limitation of this study. In order to evaluate the results and identify successes and achievements, future research could be carried out in other multinational corporations with critical threshold in other Nigerian States and also the entire Lagos State. It is possible that management accessibility and performance teams' compositions for the samples (Bua Foods, Nestle Nigeria Foods, and Nigeria Brew participants) were not entirely reflective of FMCG for the whole state of Lagos. Hence, a more thorough organisation analysis might be advantageous. Using inferential statistical approaches, it is vital to examine the causal relationship between inclusion, engagement, effectiveness, and efficiency. It is crucial to ascertain whether workplace inclusion and employee commitment provide equivalent outcomes because inclusion management boosts workplace effectiveness and strengthens the company's competitive edge. In addition to the fact that it commits employees by encouraging growth for both the individual and the organisation, it would be vital to look into the relationship between engagement, inclusivity, effectiveness, and efficiency.

References

- Adamopoulos, I. P. (2022). Job satisfaction in public health care sector, measures scales and theoretical background. *European Journal of Environment and Public Health*, 6(2), em0116.
- Ahmed, A. (2017). *Overcoming barriers to inclusive mobility: Experience of disabled people in tertiary institutions of Kano, Nigeria* [Unpublished PhD Thesis]. University of Malaya.
- Akinyemi, O. (2022). *Development of a Change Management Framework to enhance Business Model Innovation, which improves organisational performance in the Nigeria travel sector* [Unpublished PhD thesis]. University of Wales Trinity Saint David.
- Amah, O. E., & Oyetunde, K. (2020). The effect of servant leadership on employee turnover in SMEs in Nigeria: the role of career growth potential and employee voice. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 27(6), 885-904.
- Bell, K. (2021). Diversity and inclusion in environmentalism. *In diversity and inclusion in environmentalism*. Routledge.

- Brown, J. (2019). *How to be an inclusive leader: Your role in creating cultures of belonging where everyone can thrive*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- Chen, H., Liang, Q., Feng, C., & Zhang, Y. (2023). Leadership and follower voice: The role of inclusive leadership and group faultlines in promoting collective voice behaviour. *The Journal of Applied Behavioural Science*, 59(1), 61-87.
- Clement, O. I., & Eketu, C. A. (2019). Organisational climate and employee engagement in banks in rivers state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 5(3), 57-84.
- Enrique, D. V., Marcon, É., Charrua-Santos, F., & Frank, A. G. (2022). Industry 4.0 enabling manufacturing flexibility: technology contributions to individual resource and shop floor flexibility. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*.
- Falola, H. O., Ogueyungbo, O. O., & Ojebola, O. O. (2020). Influence of workplace management initiatives on talent engagement in the Nigerian pharmaceutical industry. *F1000Research*, 9.
- Fazzi, L. (2023). Introducing Creativity into Social Work Managers' Curricula: Conceptual and Practical Aspects. In *Handbook of Applied Teaching and Learning in Social Work Management Education: Theories, Methods, and Practices in Higher Education* (pp. 113-129). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Gbadegesin, J. T., Ojekalu, S., Komolafe, M. O., & Oyewole, M. O. (2022). Underlying factors for effective collective decision on community-driven infrastructure in developing countries. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 22(11), 2121-2133.
- Harry, O. O., Boma, W. E., & Magnus, O. T. (2021). Competitive risk strategy and entrepreneurial satisfaction among fast moving consuming goods in Nigeria during covid-19 pandemic using confirmatory factor analysis.
- Hasan, E. (2022). Understanding Religion, Culture, and the Role of Workplace Leadership in Nigeria. In *Embracing Workplace Religious Diversity and Inclusion: Key Challenges and Solutions* (pp. 105-117). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Javed, B., Fatima, T., Khan, A. K., & Bashir, S. (2021). Impact of inclusive leadership on innovative work behavior: the role of creative self-efficacy. *The Journal of Creative Behaviour*, 55(3), 769-782.
- Kretschmer, S. (2022). *Transformative Driving Forces in Organic Food Systems: A Roadmap toward the Sustainable Development Goals*. BoD—Books on Demand.
- Kuknor, S. C., & Bhattacharya, S. (2022). Inclusive leadership: new age leadership to foster organizational inclusion. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 46(9), 771-797.
- Mbah, S. I., & Maduafor, C. A. (2022). Knowledge management and organisational performance of pharmaceutical manufacturing firms in Enugu State, Nigeria.
- Mulugeta, Y. (2022). *Assessment of employee turnover and employee retention strategies the case of Midroc Construction Eth Plc* [Unpublished PhD thesis]. St. Mary's University.
- Nilsson, K., & Nilsson, E. (2021). Organisational measures and strategies for a healthy and sustainable extended working life and employability—a deductive content analysis with data including employees, first line managers, trade union representatives and hr-practitioners. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(11), 5626.
- Nwabueze, A. U., & Anike, A. N. (2016). Mentoring strategies in use for professional development of librarians in South-East Federal University Libraries. *Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology*, 9(1), 183-208.
- Nwankwere, I. A., Asikhia, O. U., & Adebola, S. A. (2017). Dynamic Capabilities and Firm Performance of Selected Foods and Beverages Manufacturing Companies in Lagos State, Nigeria.
- Nweke, E. O., & Umanah, R. G. (2022). Role differentiation and job performance of administrative staff in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. *African Journal of Management and Business Research*, 3(1), 59-72.

- Obiekwe, O., Zeb-Obipi, I., & Ejo-Orusa, H. (2019). Employee involvement in organisations: benefits, challenges and implications. *Management and Human Resource Research Journal*, 8(8), 1-11.
- Ogwueleka, A. C. (2015). *Evaluation of incentive mechanisms on performance-based contracting systems in South Africa and Nigeria* [Unpublished Phd thesis]. University of Pretoria.
- Okolie, U. C., Igwe, P. A., Nwosu, H. E., Eneje, B. C., & Mlanga, S. (2020). Enhancing graduate employability: Why do higher education institutions have problems with teaching generic skills? *Policy Futures in Education*, 18(2), 294-313.
- Randel, A. E., Galvin, B. M., Shore, L. M., Ehrhart, K. H., Chung, B. G., Dean, M. A., & Kedharnath, U. (2018). Inclusive leadership: Realizing positive outcomes through belongingness and being valued for uniqueness. *Human Resource Management Review*, 28(2), 190-203.
- Taufique, K. M. R. (2022). Sustainable employee green behaviour in the workplace: Integrating cognitive and non-cognitive factors in corporate environmental policy. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 31(1), 110-128.
- Schönwälder, J., & Weber, A. (2022). Maturity levels of sustainable corporate entrepreneurship: The role of collaboration between a firm's corporate venture and corporate sustainability departments. *Business Strategy and the Environment*.
- Shehu, B. G., & Clarke, M. L. (2020). Successful and sustainable crop based biodiesel programme in Nigeria through ecological optimisation and intersectoral policy realignment. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 134, 110383.
- Super, J. F. (2020). Building innovative teams: Leadership strategies across the various stages of team development. *Business Horizons*, 63(4), 553-563.
- Swanson, R. A., Holton III, E. F., & Holton, E. (1999). *Results: How to assess performance, learning, and perceptions in organisations* (Vol. 5). Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- Thompson, S., Adekoya, R., Mallick, U., Adaji, O., Rakib, A., & Carew, M. (2022). *Accessible sanitation in the workplace—important considerations for disability-inclusive employment in Nigeria and Bangladesh*. Institute of Development Studies.
- Ugoani, J. N. (2013). Ethical excellence through employee's diversity management in Nigeria. *Management and Administrative Sciences Review*, 2(4), 343-352.
- Wu, C., Su, N., Guo, W., & Wei, W. (2022). Import competition and the improvement in pollutant discharge from heterogeneous enterprises: Evidence from China. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 310, 114809.
- Wu, Q., Yan, D., & Umair, M. (2023). Assessing the role of competitive intelligence and practices of dynamic capabilities in business accommodation of SMEs. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 77, 1103-1114.
- Younas, A., Wang, D., Javed, B., & Haque, A. U. (2022). Inclusive leadership and voice behaviour: The role of psychological empowerment. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 1-17.